

ESR Study of Cu(II)-N-Aryl Glycinates

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Ten Cu(II) complexes of N-substituted phenylglycines, $RC_6H_4NHCH_2COOH$, have been synthesized (R = H, *p*-MeO, *p*-Me, *p*-Cl, *p*-NO₂, *m*-MeO, *m*-Me, *m*-Cl, *m*-NO₂, and *o*-Me). The powder esr spectra and magnetic susceptibility of these complexes have been measured and their structure and splitting of energy levels of Cu(II) ion in crystal field have been discussed in the light of the physicochemical data obtained.

ESR study is a useful method to investigate crystal structure and to determine the ground state of electrons in the metal ion. For Cu(II) ion, its six coordinated compounds can not achieve the highest symmetry O_h because of the Jahn-Teller effect; it can have only D_{4h} or lower symmetry if some other unsymmetrical factors exist. If the unpaired electron of Cu(II) occupied the d_{x²-y²} orbital as the ground state, there would be elongated distortion of the electron density of Cu(II) ion and the esr spectra would show g₁ > g_⊥. On the other hand, if d_{z²} is the ground state, there would be compressed distortion and the esr would show g₁ < g_⊥. The majority of Cu(II) complexes show g₁ > g_⊥ which means that d_{x²-y²} is commonly the ground state. In some cases, however, for complexes of g₁ < g_⊥ the ground state may still be d_{x²-y²}.

We have prepared ten Cu(II) complexes of N-substituted phenylglycines and have their powder esr spectra and magnetic susceptibility measured. Their structures and splitting of energy levels of the Cu(II) ion have been discussed.

Experimental

Preparation of N-arylglycines :

All chemicals were of reagent grade. The synthesis of N-phenylglycine and N-(*para*-substituted phenyl)glycines have been reported previ-

ously³ and the N-(*meta*-substituted phenyl)glycines are reported elsewhere³. The *ortho* substituted isomer, N-(*o*-methylphenyl)glycine, was prepared by the method of Walls⁴.

Preparation of Cu(II)-N-arylglycinates :

The ligand was dissolved in dilute NaOH solution and pH adjusted to 7-8. To the ligand solution was added a half-equimolar solution of Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O. After 10 min of stirring the precipitate was filtered off and washed with water until free from nitrate ion. The solid product was dried below 70° for 8-12 hr. The results of chemical analysis of these Cu(II) complexes are given in Table 1.

Physical measurements :

Magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes were measured in a Gouy balance at room temperature using double distilled water, aqueous nickel chloride solution and Ni(en)₃S₂O₈ as the calibrants. The experimental and calculated magnetic moment values are also shown in Table 1.

The powder esr spectra of the complexes were measured at room temperature with a JES-3BX ESR spectrometer, equipped with 100 KHz field modulation unit. DPPH with g=2.0036 and Mn²⁺ (MgO) were used as the standard field markers. The measured data of g₁ (or g_{||}), g₂ (or g_⊥), g₃ and g_{av} of these copper(II) complexes are given in Table 2.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF Cu(II)-N-(SUBSTITUTED PHENYL) GLYCINATES

Substituent R	Molecular formula	Analysis %				Magnetic moment (B. M.)		
		Nitrogen		Copper		Temp. K	Found	Calcd.
		Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found			
H	CuL ₂	7.70	7.63	17.46	17.53	280	1.80	1.84
<i>p</i> -MeO	"	6.61	6.80	14.99	15.03	281	1.85	"
<i>p</i> -Me	"	7.15	7.19	16.21	16.75	290	1.99	1.85
<i>p</i> -Cl	"	6.47	6.55	14.68	14.88	291	1.88	1.94
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	CuL ₂ ·4H ₂ O	10.65	10.79	12.08	12.09	290	1.95	1.85
<i>m</i> -MeO	CuL ₂ ·2H ₂ O	6.09	6.24	13.82	14.16	285	1.88	"
<i>m</i> -Me	CuL ₂	7.15	7.44	16.21	16.15	284	1.94	"
<i>m</i> -Cl	CuL ₂ ·2H ₂ O	5.98	6.26	13.56	13.58	289	1.91	1.84
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	CuL ₂ ·2H ₂ O	11.44	11.43	12.97	13.16	281	1.85	"
<i>o</i> -Me	CuL ₂	7.15	7.00	16.21	16.14	285	1.85	"

TABLE 2—ESR DATA OF Cu(II)-N-(SUBSTITUTED PHENYL)GLYCINATES

Ligand	g_1 (or g_2)	g_2 (or g_1)	g_3	g_{av}	ξ/Δ_1	ξ/Δ_2	ξ/Δ_3
PG	2.2248 ± 0.0020	2.0646 ± 0.0003		2.1193	0.02781	0.03115	
<i>p</i> -MeOPG	2.2256 ± 0.0030	2.0664 ± 0.0003		2.1208	0.02791	0.03205	
<i>p</i> -MePG	2.2273 ± 0.0020	2.0667 ± 0.0005		2.1216	0.02813	0.03220	
<i>p</i> -CIPG	2.2403	2.0854 ± 0.0005		2.1383	0.02975	0.04155	
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ PG	2.4351 ± 0.0040	2.0599 ± 0.0030		2.2421	0.05410	0.02880	
<i>m</i> -MeOPG	2.2472 ± 0.0030	2.0936 ± 0.0004	2.0532 ± 0.0004	2.1330	0.03061	0.04565	0.02545
<i>m</i> -MePG	2.2338 ± 0.0010	2.0770 ± 0.0010		2.1305	0.02894	0.03735	
<i>m</i> -CIPG	2.2488 ± 0.0040	2.0787 ± 0.0006		2.1369	0.03081	0.03870	
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ PG	2.2037 ± 0.0006	2.1151 ± 0.0006	2.0715 ± 0.0009	2.1298	0.02480	0.05640	0.03460
<i>o</i> -MePG	2.1756 ± 0.0030	2.0657 ± 0.0030		2.1264	0.02166	0.03170	

Results and Discussion

For copper(II) ion in a crystal field, the magnetic moment (μ) was calculated by the first approximation method⁶.

$$\mu^2 = 3/4 g_{av}^2 \dots (1)$$

$$g_{av}^2 = 1/3(g_1^2 + g_2^2 + g_3^2) \dots (2)$$

In a D_{4h} field, $g_1 = g_2$, $g_3 = g_3 = g_1$. By substituting the g values obtained from esr spectra into the above equations, the corresponding μ values were calculated which are listed in the last column of Table 1.

It is seen from Table 2 that $g_1 > g_1$ for all the copper(II) complexes of N-arylglycines, which implies that the 3d unpaired electron of Cu(II) ion should occupy the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital and it would have elongated distorted octahedral conformation. As $d_{x^2-y^2}$ is the ground state, the g 's in a D_{4h} symmetry field should be

$$g_1 = g_e + \frac{8\xi}{\Delta_1} \dots (3)$$

Fig. 2.

$$g_1 = g_e + \frac{2\xi}{\Delta_1} \dots (4)$$

while in a D_{2h} symmetry field,

$$g_1 = g_e + \frac{8\xi}{\Delta_1} \dots (5)$$

$$g_2 = g_e + \frac{2\xi}{\Delta_2} \dots (6)$$

$$g_3 = g_e + \frac{2\xi}{\Delta_3} \dots (7)$$

where g_e is the g value of free electron ($g_e = 2.0023$) and ξ is the spin-orbit coupling constant which is taken as 830 cm^{-1} for the free copper(II) ion. The significance of Δ value is shown in Fig. 1.

The various g values were obtained from esr spectra. When these g values were substituted into the above equations, the corresponding ξ/Δ values

Fig. 1. Ligand field splitting of d-orbitals in Cu(II) complexes.

were obtained which are shown in the last three columns in Table 2.

The shapes of the esr spectra of the complexes are shown in Fig. 2.

In Fig. 2,(a) shows an axial pattern which suggests that the four atoms (N, N, O, O) are coplanar and are about equidistant from copper atom. Since the powder technique is not sensitive enough to resolve the two planar components (Cu—O, Cu—N), so that, should the true symmetry of these complexes be D_{2h} (*trans* configuration with six- or four-coordination) or even lower (*cis* configuration or *trans* configuration with five-coordination), the poor resolution obtained would still justify the use of D_{4h} symmetry.

These complexes may be considered to have the normal amino acid chelate type of structure (I of Fig. 3) in which the aromatic nitrogen atom and one of the carboxyl oxygen atoms act as donors while additional water molecules or the C=O oxygen atoms of neighbouring molecules further coordinated along the axis normal to the molecular

plane to form an elongated octahedral or square-based pyramidal configuration.

It is seen from Table 2 that for these complexes $\xi'/\Delta_{\parallel} < \xi'/\Delta_{\perp}$ which means $\Delta_{\parallel} > \Delta_{\perp}$ indicating the 2E_g level lies below the ${}^2B_{2g}$ level, and the order of the energy levels is

$${}^2B_{1g}(d_{x^2-y^2}) < {}^2A_{1g}(d_{z^2}) < {}^2E_g(d_{xz}, d_{yz}) < {}^2B_{2g}(d_{xy})$$

When $R = m\text{-MeO}$, $m\text{-NO}_2$, [(b) and (c) in Fig. 2], the esr spectra exhibit three g values which fact indicates that the symmetry of these two complexes is lower than D_{4h} and their molecules would show a rhombic distortion due to the difference in Cu-O and Cu-N bond lengths. It is interesting to note that, although $m\text{-MeO}$ group has lower electron attracting ability than $m\text{-Cl}$ group⁸, the esr spectra showed that the latter complex still has the same configuration as the unsubstituted Cu(II)-N-phenylglycine complex, which indicates that in addition to the effect of electron density change on the nitrogen atom of the ligand there must be some steric effect to elongate the Cu-N bond. It may also arise from different geometrical arrangement of the ligands in the complexes⁷.

A comparison of the ξ'/Δ values shows that the energy level sequences of these two complexes are as follows :

For Cu(II)- $m\text{-MeO}_2$ PG complex :

$$d_{x^2-y^2} < d_{z^2} < d_{xz} < d_{xy} < d_{yz}$$

For Cu(II)- $m\text{-NO}_2$ PG complex :

$$d_{x^2-y^2} < d_{z^2} < d_{xz} < d_{yz} < d_{xy}$$

The esr spectra of Cu(II)- $o\text{-MePG}$ complex [(d) in Fig. 2] are quite different from the above mentioned types, suggesting low symmetry of the molecule and presence of exchange coupling⁸. According to Graddon⁹, although there was no difficulty in making a four-coordinated model of chelate amino acid structure with *ortho* substituted N-aryl-glycinates, the substituents blocked access to the fifth and sixth coordination positions of the Cu(II) ion and also restricted the free rotation of the aryl group. Therefore, the *ortho* substituted ligand should form a different configuration with Cu(II) ion than the other ligands. However, because of its weak chelating ability the *ortho* substituted ligand can hardly form a square planar configuration but very likely form a flattened tetrahedron with the four atoms (N, N, O, O) sitting out of a plane. This is a model of complex compounds having lower symmetry than the rest of the above mentioned complexes.

The esr spectra of the Cu(II)- $p\text{-NO}_2$ PG complex [(e) in Fig. 2] is analogous to that of Cu(II)- $o\text{-MePG}$ but with broader shoulder. Its line intensity was too weak to compare with the others and it became necessary to use larger quantity of sample to run the spectra. This means that the density of unpaired electron is very small. It may be ascribed to the strong electron attracting power of the *p*-nitro group

that greatly reduces the electron density on the aromatic nitrogen atom of the amino acid and thus decreases its coordinating ability with Cu(II) ion. The complex can hardly be consistent with chelation of the amino acid type but most probably having a structure of the alkanoate type (II in Fig. 3) with

Fig. 3.

the aromatic nitrogen atom being non-donor. In this structure the distance between two copper atoms is short and exchange interaction exists so that a δ -bond can form by lateral overlap of the $3d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals of the adjacent copper atoms in the dimerized molecule.

An essential feature for interpreting the esr spectra of Cu(II)-amino acid complexes is the magnitude of parameter $\Delta g_{\parallel}$ ($\Delta g_{\parallel} = g_{\parallel} - g_{\perp}$). From equations (2), (3) and (4) it is seen that the reduction in $\Delta g_{\parallel}$ values may be due to an increase in Δ or a decrease in ξ or a combination of both. An increase in Δ and (or) a decrease in ξ will lead to increase in covalency of the coordination bonding so as to increase the extent of delocalization of electrons from metal to ligand. On the other hand, a decrease in Δ and (or) an increase in ξ will lead to increase in ionic character of the coordination bonding. Therefore, a plot of $\Delta g_{\parallel}$ against Δg_{av} may reflect the extent of covalency in the Cu(II) complexes formed with different N-aryl-glycines. Fig. 4

Fig. 4.

1. Glycine, 2. PG, 3. *p*-MeOPG, 4. *p*-MePG, 5. *m*-MePG, 6. *p*-ClPG, 7. *m*-ClPG.

shows such a plot, which indicates that an introduction of electron attracting group into the phenyl radical leads to increase ionic character of the metal-ligand bond. A comparison of Cu(glycine)₂¹⁰ with

Cu(N-aryl-glycine)₂ shows that the former complex has higher covalency than the latter.

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